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An Explorative Study on Norwegian Users’ Understandings and Practices of Vacuum Toilet Systems in Private and Semi-Private Residences

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Abstract

Sustainability and sustainable development are prominent topics of interest in the world. The sixth and eleventh targets of the Sustainable Development Goals are to have adequate clean water and hygiene and have sustainable communities, respectively. Vacuum toilet systems save water and can facilitate nutrient recovery thus they aid at sustainability at a community level. The purposes of this thesis were to 1) Describe the perceptions, knowledge, and beliefs Norwegians have of vacuum toilet systems in comparison to conventional flush toilets; 2) Explore external factors influencing routine practices towards vacuum toilet use; 3) Identify key barriers to vacuum toilet system acceptance; and 4) Identify comfort levels regarding the possible integration of the model of ecological sanitation in residences. A qualitative research study was completed through the use of in-depth interviews for data collection among vacuum toilet users in the Norwegian communities of Kaja, Ås and Torvetua, Bergen. Interview transcripts were analysed using a thematic approach to understand the practices of the vacuum toilet system and identify factors that influenced the practices and perspectives of vacuum toilet system users. Concepts rooted in the social sciences were used as analytical tools to interpret the data.

Technical aspects and personal practice were found to have influenced the users' perceptions and practice of the system, and future development of vacuum systems.

Technical complications and the blueprint of the vacuum system significantly affected users' practices and experiences. Semi-private or private residency status was a factor in the practice and perceptions of vacuum toilet systems. Noise from the vacuum toilets, and smell from the holding tanks, were reported to be the key aspects participants reported for not accepting vacuum toilet systems for future development.

The research study concludes that despite the complications and concerns, the users were overall satisfied with the vacuum toilet system. Going forward, it is important to consider the implications of the technical aspects of the vacuum toilet systems in both communities in conjunction with user practice and experience. Further improvement of the vacuum toilets should specifically be rooted in addressing noise and the technical complications with the system to enhance user compliance and acceptance.

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Abbreviations

CFS:	Conventional flush system (used interchangeably with traditional, common, or water flush)
Eco-San:	Ecological sanitation
EU:	European Union
mm:	millimetres
NMBU:	Norwegian University of Life Sciences
NIBIO:	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
SDG:	Sustainable Development Goals
VTS:	Vacuum toilet system

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	I
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	II
ABBREVIATIONS	III
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY	3
1.2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS	4
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 INTRODUCTION	6
2.2 CONCEPT OF VACUUM TOILETS	6
2.3 ECOLOGICAL SANITATION (ECO-SAN)	8
2.4 USER COMPLIANCE AND ACCEPTANCE	9
2.4.1 APPROACHES IN PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY.....	11
2.6 THE NORWEGIAN CONTEXT	13
2.7 GAPS IN THE LITERATURE.....	14
CHAPTER THREE: STUDY AREAS AND POPULATIONS	15
3.1 KAJA STUDENT HOUSING, ÅS.....	15
3.2 TORVETUA, BERGEN.....	16
3.3. COMPARISONS	17
CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY	19
4.1 PROJECT CONTEXT	19
4.2 STUDY DESIGN AND RATIONALE	19
4.3 THEORETICAL APPROACH.....	20
4.4 PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT.....	21
4.4.1 <i>Participant inclusion criteria</i>	22
4.5 IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS	22
4.6 DATA COLLECTION	23
4.7 DATA ANALYSIS	24
4.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	25
4.9 LIMITATIONS.....	26
CHAPTER FIVE: RESULTS	27
5.1 INTRODUCTION	27
5.2 TECHNICAL ASPECTS	28
5.2.1 <i>Physical properties</i>	28
5.2.2 <i>Complications</i>	31
5.2.3 <i>System blueprint</i>	33
5.3 PERSONAL PRACTICES OF THE SYSTEM	37
5.3.1 <i>Cleaning practices</i>	37
5.3.2 <i>Preventative measures</i>	38
5.3.3 <i>Daily flushing behaviours</i>	42
5.4 PERSONAL PERCEPTIONS	47
5.4.1 <i>Knowledge of the system</i>	47
5.4.2 <i>Opinions of the system</i>	50
5.4.3 <i>Personal preference</i>	54

5.4.4 <i>Future of vacuum toilet systems</i>	57
5.4.5 <i>Future implementation of ecological sanitation</i>	64
5.5 SOCIAL ASPECTS	67
5.5.1 <i>Awareness</i>	68
5.5.2 <i>Collaboration and collective action</i>	68
5.5.3 <i>Social bonding and unity</i>	70
CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSION	73
6.1 TECHNICALITIES OF THE VACUUM TOILET SYSTEMS.....	73
6.2 COMPLICATIONS AND USER PRACTICES	76
6.3 PRACTICES AND PERCEPTIONS	78
6.4 PRACTICES AND RESIDENCY STATUS	82
CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	84
REFERENCES	87
APPENDICES	94
APPENDIX A- NSD APPROVAL	94
APPENDIX B- RECRUITMENT LETTER AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM (KAJA).....	96
APPENDIX C- RECRUITMENT LETTER AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM (TORVETUA).....	99
APPENDIX D- PRE- INTERVIEW PROJECT INFORMATION AND VERBAL CONSENT.....	103
APPENDIX E- INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	105